

Real Time Cyber Situational Awareness for 6G Networks Leveraging Spatial Metrics

José Antonio Pastor Valera, Martin Husák, Jesús García Rodríguez, Jorge Bernal Bernabé, and Antonio Skarmeta

Abstract—The dynamic and heterogeneous nature of 6G networks demands continuous, real-time cyber situational awareness (CSA) to support cognitive security operations such as behavior analysis, threat hunting, and adaptive defense. Traditional CSA frameworks like CRUSOE capture structural and mission-level data but cannot process the dynamic, high-frequency telemetry typical of 6G environments. This paper presents the Extended Infrastructure and Service Information Model (EISIM) and its implementation within a Cyber Situational Awareness Platform (CSAP) designed for real-time, context-aware security management. CSAP aggregates and models data from diverse sources into a unified graph representing assets, flows, services, and vulnerabilities, enabling continuous assessment of operational and security posture. The platform introduces novel spatial risk metrics, including Flow Load Centrality and Operational Risk Centrality, which integrate topological position, traffic intensity, vulnerability exposure, and resource capacity to quantify risk, exposure, and criticality. By combining workflow-driven data collection with real-time spatial analytics, CSAP enhances situational awareness and decision-making within 6G Security Operation Centers (6G-SOCs), enabling proactive identification of critical network elements and improved resilience through cognitive, data-driven management.

Index Terms—6G Networks, Cyber Situational Awareness, Cognitive Security, Real-time Analytics, Spatial Network Metrics

I. INTRODUCTION

CYBER situational awareness (CSA) is a concept describing the ability to perceive elements of cyber environment (e.g., hosts, services, networks, vulnerabilities), comprehend their meaning, and predict future changes in the situation [1], [2]. Traditional approaches to achieve CSA usually started with mapping the networks and hosts in them and then proceeding to analyze their relationships or vulnerabilities [3], [4]. However, computer networks have become highly dynamic due to the wide spread of wireless networking (including 6G), the use of IoT and cloud, or containerized services. Thus, there is a need to dynamically update the information on the network, even to the point of acknowledging current network traffic flows.

The static network mapping and predefined assessments of traditional CSA approaches makes them ineffective for highly dynamic 6G networks with virtualized, cloud-native, and IoT components. The key gap is the inability to integrate real-time traffic analysis with structured CSA models, limiting the ability to monitor and predict security threats in these environments. Overcoming this challenge requires a more adaptive

approach that combines both perspectives for comprehensive situational awareness.

Real-time network monitoring plays a fundamental role in enabling effective security operations. Security Operation Centers rely on accurate, up-to-date knowledge of the network state—including topology, active flows, and asset vulnerabilities—to detect anomalies, correlate alerts, and respond to incidents in a timely manner. However, network and security operations have traditionally been managed in silos, limiting the ability to act on combined network and security intelligence. The integration of both perspectives has been identified as a critical requirement for modern security management [5], and directly motivates the design of a platform that continuously models the network state in support of security decision-making.

In our previous research [6], we expanded the CRUSOE infrastructure model to facilitate real-time modeling of 6G network traffic, thereby enhancing situational awareness capabilities within 6G Security Operation Centers (6G-SOCs). That study demonstrated the feasibility of capturing and modeling dynamic 6G network topologies and network traffic, providing valuable insights into context-aware and cognitive security management. The present work builds upon and substantially extends this prior research by proposing a comprehensive cyber situation awareness management framework. In particular, it introduces formal quantification of spatial network metrics and orchestrated workflows for CSA, which were not addressed in the earlier study. This extension enables a more systematic and operationally relevant approach to monitoring, analyzing, and responding to security events in 6G networks.

To fill that gap, we propose a design of a situational awareness system for 6G networks that combines the expressiveness and wide scope of CSA models known from traditional networks and the dynamic network traffic measurements used in 6G networks. Namely, our design leverages a network traffic measurement tool, Skydive, along with an extended version of ISIM data model (used in Resilmesh [7] framework) called EISIM, integrated into a Cyber Situational Awareness Platform (CSAP). Custom additions to the toolset as well as the data model are required for successful introduction of the concepts into the 6G domain. The solution is also designed as a part of wider framework known as 6G-SOC¹.

Through the integration of real-time traffic monitoring with structured CSA models, the proposed system aims to improve cyber situational awareness in 6G networks. Particularly, it is expected to improve responsiveness to network changes, scale efficiently with complex infrastructures, and improve threat

J. A. Pastor Valera, J. García Rodríguez, J. Bernal Bernabé, and A. Skarmeta are with the Department of Information and Communication Engineering, University of Murcia, Campus de Espinardo, 30100 Murcia, Spain.

M. Husák is with the Institute of Computer Science, Masaryk University, Šumavská 525/33, 602 00 Brno, Czech Republic.

¹<https://ants.inf.um.es/en/6g-soc>

detection while minimizing false positives. The system should maintain low overhead, ensure efficient data processing, and seamlessly integrate with the 6G-SOC framework to enable continuous and adaptive situational awareness.

The main results of the paper are the following:

- Proposed a novel graph-based Extended Infrastructure System Model (EISIM) for 6G networks intended to model CSA including the evolving real-time 6G network status.
- Proposed set of novel advanced spatial network CSA metrics for 6G networks that computes criticality and risk for entities.
- Design of a general algorithm and procedures for CSA intelligence management in 6G networks.
- Implementation of a platform for 6G CSA management (CSAP) and the associated enablers for real-time CSA data gathering and EISIM population, including data about topologies, vulnerabilities, system, services, network flows, and metrics quantification.
- Thorough performance evaluation of the whole solution.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II surveys the related work. The proposed approach is outlined in Section III, description of the implementation is presented in Section IV, and performance evaluation is presented in Section V. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The problem of structuring and organizing network data has been a long-standing topic of research in the field of cyber situational awareness. One of the first formal approaches was M2D2 [8], a data model for the correlation of intrusion detection systems (IDS). M2D2 formally defined a schema that integrates four complementary sources of information: system characteristics, known vulnerabilities, deployed security tools, and observed security events. Unlike earlier correlation methods, which relied solely on IDS event streams, M2D2 demonstrated how vulnerabilities and contextual information could be used to rigorously define and implement correlation examples. This marked a significant step toward more meaningful alert correlation, although it did not fully address broader aspects of network representation or mission context.

To enrich situational awareness with a broader view of the network, Virtual Terrain [9] introduced a graph-based representation of network entities and their relationships. The model captured operating systems, firewall rules, services, user accounts, and connectivity, structuring them into graphs with dynamic relationships. This allowed analysts to reason not only about vulnerabilities but also about accessibility, criticality, and dependencies across the network. By consolidating contextual information into a unified schema, Virtual Terrain sought to overcome the limitations of ad hoc feature selection, offering a more systematic approach to threat modeling and prediction.

With the increasing availability of graph databases, graph-based approaches became even more powerful and scalable. CyGraph [3] exemplified this shift by unifying data on vulnerabilities, attack paths, intrusion alerts, and mission dependencies into a knowledge graph that supported predictive and

reactive analysis. It prioritized vulnerabilities in the context of mission-critical assets, correlated ongoing attacks with known vulnerability chains, and suggested courses of action for incident response. In addition, CyGraph incorporated visualization, layering techniques and the domain-specific query language CyQL, making it possible to interactively explore the evolving attack surface and its relation to organizational missions. This work highlighted the potential of graph-based models not only for situational awareness but also for operation decision support.

Although CyGraph emphasized predictive modeling and mission assurance, the CRUSOE [10] model addressed a different challenge: how to systematically capture the heterogeneous data required for incident response. Developed in consultation with security teams, CRUSOE proposed an extensible layered data model capable of tracking missions, systems, hosts, threats, detection capabilities, and response options. Its design emphasized practical deployment in contemporary network environments, relying as much as possible on data that could be automatically or semi-automatically collected. Later, CRUSOE was implemented as an open source toolset [4], providing operators with support throughout the Observe-Orient-Decide-Act (OODA) loop. This implementation integrated monitoring, visualization, decision support, and automated orchestration to enhance the resilience of critical infrastructures.

Building on these foundations, CRUSOE evolved further into the ISIM model [7], which serves as the basis for the present work. ISIM retains the layered structure for managing heterogeneous data while extending it to support more advanced forms of situational awareness. However, despite the progress achieved by M2D2, Virtual Terrain, CyGraph, and CRUSOE, a significant limitation persists: existing models have not incorporated network flow monitoring metrics as a first-class component of situational awareness. Flow-level data, which capture communication patterns, traffic volume, and anomalies at scale, offers critical insights into ongoing operations and emerging threats. Integrating these metrics into structured models would provide a richer and more actionable understanding of network dynamics.

Research works on situational awareness in 5G networks [11] primarily focus on advanced network metrics and topology information to enable analytics and cognitive decision-making, including anomaly detection [12] through mechanisms such as the N5G NWDAF analytic function. In contrast, the approach proposed in this paper extends beyond performance and traffic oriented metrics by explicitly incorporating cybersecurity-relevant information such as vulnerabilities and their Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) [13] identifiers, Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) [14] scores, affected services, and their relation to mission objectives. This integration allows not only for anomaly detection but also for a richer security assessment that ties communication behavior to exploitable weaknesses and mission impact.

The importance of cyber situational awareness in future wireless technologies has been highlighted in the context of 5G and IoT deployments, where anomaly detection and

security monitoring are recognized as key components for achieving leadership in next-generation networks [15]. In addition, domain-specific applications of situational awareness using 5G have been proposed, such as the Back Situation Awareness (BSA) service for public safety, which uses MEC-based orchestration to improve road safety through early notification of emergency vehicles [16]. In a related work on cybersecurity in automotive environment, Grimm et al. [17] were inspired by CRUSOE data model and proposed the ASCOT, a data model for capturing the security posture in the context of vehicular networks.

Beyond public safety, the use of 5G communications to enhance situation awareness in active distribution networks has been explored, with resource-efficient frameworks proposed to support real-time data collection and emergency event handling [18]. Finally, focused efforts to integrate situational awareness models into large-scale 5G MIMO systems for safety assessment and prediction [19] demonstrate the importance of modeling and predicting complex networks behaviors. However, these approaches typically address either communication performance or security event prediction in isolation and do not comprehensively integrate network topology, flow monitoring, and cybersecurity vulnerability data into a unified situational awareness framework, which is one of the main focuses of this work.

III. DESIGN

The proposed cyber situational awareness framework is designed with three main components: the Extended Infrastructure and Service Information Model (EISIM), the Cyber Situational Awareness Platform (CSAP), and a suite of spatial network risk metrics. Together, these elements form the foundation of the 6G Security Operations Center (6G-SOC) architecture, which is illustrated in Figure 1. The EISIM provides the data modeling layer that structures heterogeneous information from multiple monitoring sources. The CSAP integrates these data streams, enabling real-time analytics, orchestration, and visualization across the 6G infrastructure. Additionally, the proposed spatial risk metrics quantify the operational and security posture of network entities, supporting cognitive decision-making and adaptive defense mechanisms. The following subsections describe how these components interact within the 6G-SOC framework to deliver end-to-end situational awareness and dynamic risk assessment.

The Extended Infrastructure and Service Information Model (EISIM) is currently being integrated into a multilayer cybersecurity architecture designed for a 6G Security Operations Center (SOC). As part of the Data & Information layer, EISIM is being developed to interact with key security components in the Reaction Plane, Monitoring & Analytics, and Operations layers. This integration aims to improve CSA by enabling the structured aggregation of security-related data from multiple sources, including security information and event management (SIEM) systems, attack surface manager, data aggregation mechanisms, topology monitoring (TM) tools, and data network monitoring (DM). Once fully implemented, EISIM will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of network

security by facilitating event correlation, network topology analysis, and vulnerability detection in multiple domains.

Topology Monitoring (TM) is responsible for tracking and managing the structure of the network, including its devices, network ports, and their interconnections. TM tools continuously update network topology maps by discovering new devices and changes in the network infrastructure. This capability helps to understand how different network components interact and provides critical data for security monitoring, anomaly detection, and threat mitigation. Data Monitoring (DM) focuses on observing and analyzing the flow of data within the managed infrastructure. It shows insight into network behavior by detecting anomalies, collecting statistics on network activity, and identifying potential threats. By integrating with EISIM, DM improves the detection of suspicious patterns and facilitates proactive security measures.

In addition, a variety of connectors can be integrated to obtain infrastructure information and improve context awareness. These include active discovery tools such as Nmap² or Skydive³, and other network scanning solutions that identify topology and exposed services. Passive monitoring solutions can collect telemetry from network devices, and network analysis tools can improve visibility into dynamic virtualized environments. Monitoring connectors, such as flow data connectors (e.g. Skydive or Flowmon⁴), can be integrated to analyze traffic patterns and detect anomalies in real time.

EISIM acts as a central aggregator and processor of security-related data within the 6G-SOC framework. In addition, EISIM integrates with AI-driven analytics engines, such as the Security Analytics Engine (SAE) and AI-driven Decision (AID) components, to enhance security intelligence and enable proactive threat detection and response. These components (TM and DM) are distributed throughout the 6G network, ensuring broad coverage and real-time monitoring. Beyond monitoring, dedicated components assess risk and confidence based on EISIM analytics and make informed decisions to dynamically act on the network. In addition, orchestrators and playbook tools enforce security actions across multiple enablers and controllers, automating responses and mitigation strategies across multiple domains.

All in all, the integration of the EISIM model and CSA capabilities into the 6G-SOC framework provides a unified view of network security and helps to build a more agile and resilient defense strategy, providing a perfect baseline for anticipating threats and designing and targeting mitigation actions.

A. EISIM Data Model

In this work, we develop and apply an extended version of the ISIM data model, called EISIM, designed for assessing the network security situation within the Resilmesh EU project⁵. EISIM is a direct successor to the CRUSOE data model [10], inheriting its graph-based approach—nodes represent entities

²<https://nmap.org/>

³<https://skydive.network/>

⁴<https://www.progress.com/flowmon>

⁵<https://resilmesh.eu>

Fig. 1. 6G-SOC framework architecture [6].

such as devices, services, and vulnerabilities, while edges represent their relationships—and extending it with additional layers, entity types, and dynamic data sources required for 6G environments. An excerpt of the EISIM data model is shown in Figure 2.

EISIM is structured into seven layers, each covering a distinct domain of cybersecurity-relevant information. The three layers most directly relevant to this work are:

- *Host layer* models hosts in the network, together with their hardware specifications, running software versions (discovered via fingerprinting [20]), block storage, virtual machines, and container workloads including Docker containers, Linux namespaces, and Kubernetes resources (pods, services, deployments, network policies, and persistent volumes).
- *Network layer* represents IP addresses, network interfaces, subnets, routing entries, domain names, and network services. Physical topology is captured through LLDP switch and port records. Network sockets are modeled alongside the processes that hold them. Kubernetes networking resources (ingresses, endpoints) are also represented.
- *Threat layer* models vulnerabilities and CVE records, including CVSS and EPSS scores. Vulnerabilities are mapped to software versions, enabling full traceability from a CVE to the hosts running the affected software [21]. CWE weaknesses and CAPEC attack patterns connect vulnerabilities to the MITRE ATT&CK framework, linking tactics, techniques, countermeasures, and security incidents detected by integrated SIEM tools such as Wazuh.

The remaining layers are described briefly. The *Access control* layer covers user accounts and privileges. The *Detection and response* layer covers intrusion detection and mitigation systems. The *System* layer models redundancies and dependencies between hosts. The *Mission* layer connects cyber assets to business missions. The *Hardware and physical* layer captures physical device location and hardware characteristics, particularly relevant in industrial OT and 6G contexts. Readers interested in further details on the foundational layers are referred to the original CRUSOE paper [10].

EISIM adds a labeling attribute to distinguish node types based on MITRE D3FEND’s Digital Artifact Ontology (DAO)⁶ and custom labels for provenance tracking (e.g., which sensor provided a given piece of information). All entities carry *first_seen* and *last_seen* timestamps, enabling temporal tracking of topology evolution and automated removal of stale data.

The EISIM implementation, based on Neo4j, exposes GraphQL and REST APIs and does not collect data itself, relying on external tools such as CASM in Resilmesh [7] or Observe in CRUSOE [4]. In CSAP, data ingestion is handled by dedicated Temporal workflows described in Section IV. A minimalist scenario includes Nmap for host and service enumeration, exporting CPE fingerprints [22], which are then used to query multiple threat intelligence sources such as NVD⁷ for relevant CVEs. All elements are stored in EISIM in their corresponding node types, optionally enriched by vulnerability scanners or host-based agents.

The basic EISIM structure described above, including the host, network, and threat layers and their integration into the CSAP platform, was first introduced in our prior conference work [6]. The present journal paper substantially extends that foundation by formally defining the *Flow* entity and its integration into the graph (Section III-B), introducing the spatial risk metrics computed over the EISIM graph (Section III-D), and providing a comprehensive performance evaluation of the full platform.

B. Extension of EISIM to Model 6G Network Flows

Although the EISIM graph captures a rich static picture of the network, its security value significantly enhanced by incorporating real-time network traffic. Static snapshots cannot reveal which paths are actively carrying traffic, how load is distributed, or which nodes are currently exposed to data flows, all of which are essential for timely situational awareness in dynamic 6G environments.

To extend EISIM with this dynamic dimension, a new *Flow* entity is introduced. Each *Flow* node stores the full set of features of a captured network flow: source and destination MAC addresses, IP addresses, and ports; transport protocol; start time, duration, and finish type; packet and byte counts in both directions; and TCP-specific fields such as SYN, FIN, and RST timestamps and segment reordering indicators. The *Flow* node is then connected within the graph to the existing entities referenced in its fields: to the *IP* address nodes of its source and destinations, and to *Network Service* nodes on the corresponding end ports. This integration makes flows first-class citizens of the EISIM graph, enabling graph queries and metric computation that jointly reason over topology, services, vulnerabilities, and traffic.

In 6G networks, this integration is complicated by the nested encapsulation structure of mobile traffic. As show in Figure 3, a 6G data packet carries multiple layers of headers: an outer physical layer (MAC, IP, UDP), a tenant isolation layer (VXLAN, MAC, IP, UDP), a mobility layer (GTP, IP, UDP),

⁶<https://d3fend.mitre.org/dao/>

⁷<https://nvd.nist.gov/>

Fig. 2. An excerpt from enhanced EISIM data model: relevant entities and relationships from threat, network, and host layers and the new Flow entity.

and the application payload. Standard flow monitoring tools parse only the outermost headers, losing visibility into the inner GTP-encapsulated sessions. Our work extends Skydive to support GTP, enabling per-session flow tracking within GTP tunnels, detailed in Section IV-B. While VXLAN is used here for tenant isolation, the approach generalizes to other encapsulation protocols.

C. CSAP Workflow-Based Architecture

The Cyber Situational Awareness Platform (CSAP) is a containerized, workflow-driven architecture that aggregates, processes, and maintains cyber situational awareness information from a variety of infrastructure and external data sources. Based on EISIM, CSAP provides a unified, graph-based representation of assets, services, vulnerabilities, and network flows across the monitored environment. This model provides a consistent, interconnected view of static and dynamic network components, enabling continuous assessment of the system’s operational and security state.

CSAP operates within a containerized environment that separates its primary functional domains into modular, independently deployable components, as shown in Figure 4. This design ensures scalability, fault tolerance, and ease of maintenance. Each core capability—workflow execution, data collection, analytics, and visualization—functions within its own isolated container. Consequently, updates, restarts, or scaling operations can be performed without affecting other components, thereby maintaining a consistent and reliable flow of data throughout the system.

The architecture is founded on infrastructure and data sources, including 5G and 6G devices, hosts, networks, namespaces, containers, and vulnerability databases. CSAP uses

these sources to develop a comprehensive understanding of the monitored environment. Specialized crawlers collect and normalize data from these sources, forming the data collection layer. This layer includes several dedicated components, including the topology crawler, the vulnerabilities and CVEs crawler, and the network flows crawler. Each performs targeted retrieval operations to capture information relevant to the network’s structural and behavioral aspects. In addition, CSAP integrates with external data collection systems such as Skydive and Nmap, extending its visibility beyond the local infrastructure.

The selection of Skydive as the network monitoring backend was made after evaluating several candidate tools. Flow-oriented solutions such as ntopng⁸ and NetFlow/IPFIX collectors (e.g., nfdump⁹) provide rich traffic statistics but offer no native topology representation, making it difficult to correlate flows with network structure. Security-focused frameworks such as Zeek¹⁰ provide deep packet inspection and event generation but are similarly topology-unaware and not designed for graph-based CSA models. General-purpose observability frameworks such as OpenTelemetry¹¹ lack built-in network flow capture and are not tailored to security contexts. SNMP-based monitoring platforms such as Zabbix¹² support topology discovery but rely on periodic polling, which is insufficient for the real-time requirements of 6G-SOC environments. Skydive was selected because it uniquely combines real-time topology graph construction with integrated flow capture, exposes a REST API suitable for programmatic integration with CSAP

⁸<https://www.ntop.org/products/traffic-analysis/ntopng/>

⁹<https://github.com/phaag/nfdump>

¹⁰<https://zeek.org>

¹¹<https://opentelemetry.io>

¹²<https://www.zabbix.com>

Fig. 3. 6G packet header representation.

Fig. 4. Layered overview of the CSAP architecture, showing data flow from infrastructure and data sources through collection and processing workflows to the EISIM graph model.

workflows, and is open-source, which allowed the GTP protocol extensions described in Section IV-B to be implemented directly in its source code.

The CSAP workflow execution environment orchestrates these data collection processes and governs workflow runtimes, activity workers, logging, monitoring, and internal dashboards. Within this environment, all data interactions are controlled through workflows rather than static connectors. Each workflow independently retrieves, transforms, and stores data in accordance with the EISIM schema. This workflow-based approach provides a high degree of flexibility and extensibility, enabling the integration of new data sources without modifying the platform’s underlying components.

After collection, the data is enriched and processed within the workflow environment before being integrated into the platform’s data workloads. These workloads consist primarily of a graph database and spatial metrics repositories. The graph database stores structured representations of entities, relationships, and contextual attributes. The spatial metrics component computes proximity, exposure, and connectivity measures. Analytics workflows operate directly upon these data workloads,

performing higher-level reasoning and computation to derive insights such as asset exposure levels, communication density metrics, and composite risk indicators.

Processed and enriched information stored in the graph database is accessible via standardized interfaces, such as REST and Graph APIs, SOC operator tools, and visualization dashboards. These interfaces provide analysts and automated systems direct access to the EISIM-based knowledge graph, allowing them to explore the network’s structure, trace vulnerabilities, monitor dynamic conditions, and identify emerging risks.

D. Advanced Novel Spatial Metrics for Real-Time Contextual Awareness

Our proposal seeks several benefits for cognitive network management. The knowledge of the specific flows that are continuously traversing every point in a 6G network can significantly increase the capabilities of detection of anomalies and cyberattacks. Information about the current status of the traffic, when combined with the vulnerabilities and services in each node of the data path of the flow, further enhances the intelligence capabilities. Furthermore, this contextual data can provide meaningful information for making decisions about possible prevention actions and countermeasures against ongoing attacks.

In this same direction, spatial network metrics, such as betweenness centrality [11]—traditionally based on static network topologies—can now be weighted by the number of flows at every particular point of the network. This new kind of metric can provide the evolving importance and criticality of each node in real time. These new sophisticated types of metrics can influence the risk assessment component of the architecture in charge of computing risk per node and service.

This approach is based on representing the network as a weighted, directed graph $G = (N, E)$, where N is the set of network nodes and E is the set of directed edges connecting them. Each edge $e \in E$ is associated with a weight that can represent latency, cost, or any other relevant link metric, and may also store information such as capacity and current utilization. All subsequent metrics are defined over this graph and are periodically recomputed as the network evolves.

The first and most fundamental metric is the betweenness centrality of a node, denoted as $BC(v)$. It quantifies the extent to which a given node lies on the shortest paths between other pairs of nodes. Formally, for each ordered pair of distinct source and destination nodes (s, t) , one may define $\sigma_{s,t}$ as the number of shortest paths between s and t , and $\sigma_{s,t}(v)$ as the

number of those paths that pass through v . The betweenness centrality is then expressed as:

$$BC(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{s,t}(v)}{\sigma_{s,t}} \quad (1)$$

A node with a high value of $BC(v)$ therefore acts as a topological bridge or bottleneck. Because the scale of this metric depends on the size of the graph, a normalized version is usually adopted:

$$nBC(v) = \frac{BC(v)}{\max_{u \in N} BC(u)} \quad (2)$$

This normalization constrains all values to the interval $[0, 1]$, allowing direct comparison among nodes.

While betweenness centrality reflects potential importance in terms of topology, it does not account for the actual volume of traffic that each node currently carries. To address this, a complementary measure, referred to as Flow Load Centrality and denoted $FLC(v)$, is introduced. For each node v , all flows that either originate from or are destined to any IP assigned to that node are considered. The total traffic volume associated with a node is computed as:

$$FLC(v) = \sum_{f \in F_v} ab_bytes(f) + ba_bytes(f) \quad (3)$$

where F_v denotes the set of flows linked to node v as either the source or the destination. The normalized Flow Load Centrality is:

$$nFLC(v) = \frac{FLC(v)}{\max_{u \in N} FLC(u)} \quad (4)$$

Nodes with large $nFLC(v)$ values are currently responsible for transporting a substantial portion of the total network traffic and thus represent dynamic critical points even if their static betweenness is modest.

A further dimension of node assessment concerns software vulnerability. The vulnerability data enters CSAP through the vulnerability retrieval workflow described in Section IV. For each software version identified on a node, CSAP queries multiple external vulnerability feeds and attaches the matching CVE records to the node in the EISIM graph. Each CVE carries a CVSS base score reflecting its severity. This creates a direct, traceable link from a deployed software version to its known vulnerabilities and their severity, fully integrated within the graph structure. For example, a node running an unpatched web server with three associated CVEs (CVSS scores 7.5, 6.0, and 4.0) would have its vulnerability exposure quantified and propagated into RC and SAB , directly influencing its risk ranking within the platform. For every node v , all associated CVEs are collected and the average CVSS score is normalized to the unit interval:

$$nVULN(v) = \frac{AVG(CVSS(c) \mid c \in C_v)}{10} \quad (5)$$

If no vulnerabilities exist, the value is set to 0. The average is chosen over the maximum to reflect the overall vulnerability exposure of a node rather than penalizing for a single outlier CVE, which may not be exploitable in the current network

context. This produces a smoother risk signal that is more stable under incremental vulnerability updates.

In addition to vulnerability, operation risk depends on the node's available resources. The Headroom of a node v , denoted $HR(v)$, captures this spare capacity:

$$HR(v) = 1 - \frac{used_capacity(v)}{total_capacity(v)} \quad (6)$$

Since $HR(v)$ already lies within the unit interval, it is directly used as its normalized version $nHR(v)$.

These four base quantities serve as the components of the Operational Risk Centrality, denoted $RC(v)$, subject to the constraint $\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta = 1$:

$$RC(v) = \alpha \cdot nBC(v) + \beta \cdot nFLC(v) + \gamma \cdot nVULN(v) + \delta \cdot (1 - nHR(v)) \quad (7)$$

A high value of $RC(v)$ identifies a node that simultaneously plays a central role in connectivity, transports substantial traffic, exhibits vulnerabilities, and operates close to its capacity limit. The linear combination is deliberately chosen for interpretability and computational tractability at scale. Each weight ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$) can be tuned by the security operator to reflect the relative importance of structural position, traffic load, vulnerability exposure, and resource saturation in their specific deployment. In the experiments, equal weights (0.25 each) are used as a neutral baseline.

A complementary metric called the Safe Placement Score ($SPS(v)$) is introduced to determine the suitability of each node for hosting additional workloads, with weighting coefficients $\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 = 1$:

$$SPS(v) = \omega_1 \cdot nHR(v) + \omega_2 \cdot (1 - nVULN(v)) + \omega_3 \cdot (1 - RC(v)) \quad (8)$$

Higher values indicate more secure and resource-rich nodes, suitable for deploying latency-sensitive or mission-critical services. SPS is designed as the inverse complement of RC : a node that scores high in RC (risky, loaded, vulnerable) will necessarily score low in SPS , making the two metrics jointly useful for placement decisions: RC to flag nodes to avoid routing through, SPS to identify safe candidates for service deployment.

To adjust the notion of betweenness itself to account for security and capacity, the Security-Aware Betweenness ($SAB(v)$) is formulated:

$$SAB(v) = nBC(v) \cdot (1 - nVULN(v)) \cdot nHR(v) \quad (9)$$

A node retains a high SAB only if it simultaneously exhibits high structural centrality, low vulnerability, and ample headroom. Unlike RC , SAB uses a multiplicative formulation so that a node with any disqualifying property—low structural centrality, high vulnerability, or low headroom—is strongly penalized. A single zero term collapses SAB to zero, enforcing a strict conjunction of desirable properties. This makes SAB suitable as a hard filter for security-critical routing decisions.

The metrics are designed to be both stable and consistent. RC , SPS , and SAB are deterministic of the current graph snapshot: given the same input, they always produce the same output. Score variation over time reflects genuine changes in

the underlying network (e.g., new flows, updated vulnerabilities, or resource consumption changes) rather than algorithmic instability; this dynamism is a deliberate feature of a real-time situational awareness system. Furthermore, there are no feedback loops between metric values and the graph state: CSAP is a monitoring and awareness platform that computes and exposes metrics to operators, but does not autonomously act on them. Since no agent modifies the graph based on metric outputs, contradictory or competing decisions cannot arise by design. Moreover, the dynamic nature of the metrics is itself a key advantage over static risk assessment approaches. In traditional CSA frameworks, risk scores are computed once from a fixed topology snapshot and remain unchanged until a manual reassessment is triggered. In contrast, CSAP recomputes metrics at every workflow cycle, meaning that a sudden increase in traffic load—reflected in a rising $nFLC$ —will immediately elevate the RC of the affected nodes. This temporal sensitivity enables anomaly detection based on risk score evolution: for example, a node experiencing an abnormal surge in flows between two consecutive snapshots will exhibit an atypical RC spike, which can be flagged as a potential indicator of compromise even in the absence of known attack signatures.

Beyond the node-level indicators, the criticality of services is evaluated. The Service Criticality $SC(s)$ is defined as:

$$SC(s) = \lambda \cdot I(s) + (1 - \lambda) \cdot V(s) \quad (10)$$

where $I(s)$ represents the normalized operational importance of the service, $V(s)$ is the normalized vulnerability, and λ is a weighting factor. The vulnerability component is:

$$V(s) = \frac{1}{|C_s|} \sum_{c \in C_s} \frac{CVSS(c)}{10} \quad (11)$$

The Network Service Criticality ($NSC(s)$) modulates service criticality by network centrality and load:

$$NSC(s) = SC(s) \cdot [\alpha \cdot \overline{nBC}_s + \beta \cdot \overline{nFLC}_s] \quad (12)$$

where \overline{nBC}_s and \overline{nFLC}_s are the mean normalized betweenness and flow load of nodes hosting service s , and $\alpha + \beta = 1$. The mean is taken over all nodes hosting services because a service's network exposure is collectively determined by the infrastructure it relies on. Using the mean rather than the maximum avoids over-penalizing services that are partially hosted on well-positioned nodes alongside less central ones, providing a balanced view of the service's overall network footprint.

Finally, the Aggregated Infrastructure Criticality ($AIC(s)$) integrates infrastructure reliability across the dependency chain:

$$AIC(s) = NSC(s) \cdot \sum_{l \in L_s} w_l \cdot R(l) \quad (13)$$

where L_s is the ordered set of infrastructure layers supporting service s , $R(l)$ is the operational risk of each layer, and $\sum_l w_l = 1$. Through this layered formulation, CSAP provides a unified and extensible means to quantify risk and criticality across different abstraction levels of a modern networked system.

E. Workflows Execution and Spatial Metrics Calculation Algorithm

The Cyber Situational Awareness Platform (CSAP) is a workflow-driven system designed to orchestrate multiple processes and achieve comprehensive situational awareness in complex networked environments. Algorithm 1 presents a unified, abstract algorithmic representation of key activities performed by CSAP, emphasizing the logical sequence of operations and the interaction between data collection, graph construction, and metric computation.

Algorithm 1 Proposed CSAP algorithm: topology, flows, vulnerabilities, and metric computation.

Require: Monitoring endpoints M_{net} , telemetry collectors M_{flow} , vulnerability feeds V_{feed} , metric period T_{metric} , concurrency policy Π

Ensure: Continuously updated EISIM graph G with node and service metrics, and mapped vulnerabilities

```

1: Initialize graph  $G \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: while CSAP is active do
3:    $T \leftarrow$  FetchTopologySnapshot( $M_{net}$ )
4:    $(V_T, E_T) \leftarrow$  ParseTopology( $T$ )
5:   UpdateGraph( $G, V_T, E_T$ )
6:    $F \leftarrow$  FetchFlowTelemetry( $M_{flow}$ )
7:    $(V_F, E_F) \leftarrow$  ExtractActiveFlows( $F$ )
8:   UpdateGraph( $G, V_F, E_F$ )
9:    $S \leftarrow$  GetNewSoftwareVersions( $G$ )
10:   $B \leftarrow$  BatchVersions( $S, \Pi.batch\_size$ )
11:  for all batch  $b \in B$  in parallel (max  $\Pi.workers$ ) do
12:     $R_b \leftarrow$  QueryVulnerabilityFeed( $V_{feed}, b$ )
13:    AttachVulnerabilities( $G, R_b$ )
14:  end for
15:  for all node  $v \in G.V$  in parallel do
16:     $rc \leftarrow RC(v, G)$ 
17:     $sab \leftarrow SAB(v, G)$ 
18:     $sps \leftarrow SPS(v, G)$ 
19:    UpdateNode( $v, rc, sab, sps$ )
20:  end for
21:  for all service  $s$  in  $G$  do
22:     $nsc \leftarrow NSC(s, G)$ 
23:     $aic \leftarrow AIC(s, G)$ 
24:    UpdateService( $s, nsc, aic$ )
25:  end for
26:  PersistGraph( $G$ )
27:  Sleep( $T_{metric}$ )
28: end while

```

The algorithm represents CSAP's cyclic and concurrent workflow model. The process begins with initializing the EISIM graph, which provides a unified representation of network nodes, services, vulnerabilities, and flows. Dedicated workflows operate asynchronously to retrieve the network topology, collect real-time flow telemetry, and query vulnerability information from external sources. Once the graph is updated, spatial and service-level metrics are periodically computed. These values are stored directly in the graph, enriching the EISIM model with actionable intelligence. Overall, the algorithm shows how multiple workflows are integrated

into one coherent CSAP system that continuously monitors infrastructure, analyzes collected data, and derives insights while maintaining scalability and concurrency control.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

This section details the implementation of CSAP and its extensions to the EISIM model for 6G network monitoring and traffic analysis. It focuses on the integration of Temporal¹³ workflows dedicated to scanning and processing topology information—such as hosts, interfaces, and containers—, network flows, services running on each of these hosts, and vulnerabilities associated to the software versions present on them. In addition, modifications to Skydive’s source code are described, extending its capabilities to analyze GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP) [23] traffic and overcoming a key limitation in the handling of encapsulation protocols.

A. Network Topology Scanning, Processing and Gathering Related Assets

As part of the EISIM model extension, a Python-based platform was developed to connect with the Skydive API. This integration is orchestrated using Temporal workflows, enabling robust and fault-tolerant execution of data collection and processing tasks. Specifically, one workflow includes an activity that retrieves network topology data from Skydive, such as hosts and their associated interfaces, addresses, Docker containers, etc., while another workflow gathers flow-level information and maps it to corresponding network interfaces, IP addresses, or services.

A scheduled workflow, *SkydiveTopologyWorkflow*, periodically polls the Skydive API via its Python client, which provides access to the REST interface. The workflow retrieves detailed topology information, including host attributes such as IP addresses, interfaces, neighbors, hardware specifications, operating system, and kernel version. From this data, the workflow derives additional context, identifying the Docker containers running on each host, as well as their network interfaces and addresses.

The processed topology is stored in Neo4j, where hosts, containers, interfaces, IP addresses, services, and related entities are represented as graph nodes. The relationships between these entities are modeled based on network connectivity and container deployment, as illustrated in Figure 5. Some relationships, such as those between a host and its interfaces, IP addresses, or hosted services, are time-based. When a link is created, a timestamp is attached to the relationship. This temporal information enables the EISIM model to track the evolution of the topology and allows the *CleanerWorkflow* to periodically remove stale relationships, ensuring that the graph remains consistent and up-to-date.

Network traffic is collected by a separate workflow, *SkydiveNetworkFlowsWorkflow*, which retrieves Skydive flow records, capturing attributes such as source and destination IPs, ports, protocols, and traffic metrics. When persisting these records, the workflow not only stores the flows, but also creates

Fig. 5. Sequence diagram of CSAP retrieving network topology from Skydive.

Fig. 6. Sequence diagram of CSAP retrieving CVEs and vulnerabilities for software versions stored on its database.

explicit relationships from each flow to the specific origin and destination entities, enriching the static topology with precise, queryable communication semantics.

CSAP complements this passive collection with active data enrichment workflows. The *NmapServicesWorkflow* performs active fingerprinting by scanning hosts to identify running services and their associated software components (CPEs). Alongside this, the *EasyEASMWorkflow* integrates the attack surface management tool EasyEASM¹⁴ to expand visibility beyond the internal topology. Furthermore, the *VulnerabilitiesWorkflow* leverages an external tool, search_vulns¹⁵, to retrieve CVEs associated with each software version stored in the CSAP database, as illustrated in Figure 6. This workflow integrates data from multiple sources, including the National Vulnerability Database (NVD), VulnCheck NVD++, Exploit-DB, PoC-in-GitHub, and the GitHub Security Advisory Database.

After retrieving the vulnerability intelligence, the workflow persists the results in the CSAP graph database following

¹⁴<https://github.com/g0ldencybersec/EasyEASM>

¹⁵https://github.com/ra1nb0rn/search_vulns

¹³<https://temporal.io/>

the EISIM data model. Each CVE and its corresponding vulnerability record are created as graph nodes, along with explicit relationships linking the CVE to vulnerabilities and the vulnerabilities to the specific software versions they affect.

B. Handling 6G Network Flow Traffic

Skydive is a powerful network monitoring tool designed to provide real-time visibility into network traffic and topologies. Through its distributed probe architecture, Skydive is able to classify Layer 2 through Layer 4 (L2-L4) traffic and track flows even across encapsulated paths. Skydive includes support for multiple encapsulation protocols: Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE) [24], Virtual eXtensible LAN (VXLAN) [25], Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation (Geneve) [26], and Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) [27]. However, Skydive lacked support for the GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP), which is essential for 6G mobile network traffic analysis.

To address this limitation, modifications were introduced to Skydive’s packet processing pipeline, flow tracking mechanisms, and encapsulation handling. These enhancements allow Skydive to accurately identify, process and visualize GTP tunnels, providing a deeper insight into mobile network traffic.

One of the biggest challenges in supporting GTP was ensuring that Skydive could correctly identify and differentiate GTP-encapsulated traffic. Since GTP encapsulates multiple subscriber sessions within a single UDP flow (typically over port 2152), an approach was needed to accurately track these individual sessions.

Modifications to the `TransportFlow` function enable the detection of GTP-U packets by identifying `layers.LayerTypeGTPv1U` as the last layer of the packet. The tunnel endpoint identifier (TEID) is extracted from the GTP header, similar to how VXLAN and Geneve use virtual network identifiers (VNI) to distinguish flows. This enhancement allows Skydive to track GTP flows per session rather than treating all GTP traffic as a single UDP flow.

Furthermore, the `networkID` function has been updated to support GTP tunnels. Previously, it extracted VNIs for VXLAN and Geneve, or GRE keys for GRE tunnels; the logic has been extended to retrieve the TEID for GTP packets, ensuring that Skydive correctly associates tunneled traffic with its corresponding sessions in a mobile network.

Other enhancements have been made to Skydive’s packet sequence processing logic in the `PacketSeqFromGoPacket` function. The GTP feature was extended by adding `layers.LayerTypeGTPv1U` to the list of encapsulation protocols. As a result, when a GTP packet is detected, Skydive now properly separates the encapsulated inner packet from the outer transport flow, correctly extracting and analyzing the inner payload. This enhancement is particularly relevant in mobile networks, where user traffic is encapsulated within GTP tunnels between core network elements.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of the CSAP framework and its underlying EISIM model through

a series of targeted experiments. The analysis focuses on four principal aspects. First, the proposed advanced spatial metrics are assessed and compared against betweenness centrality, which serves as the baseline. Second, the efficiency of CSAP in retrieving software vulnerabilities is examined under varying numbers of stored software versions. Third, scalability tests are conducted by incrementally increasing the number of gNBs and UEs. Finally, the latency introduced during the parsing of 6G traffic is measured.

A. Testbed

To ensure realism in the evaluation, the experiments were conducted using data collected from a physical test environment comprising 100 deployed User Equipments (UEs). From this real dataset, an augmented network dataset was programmatically generated to simulate progressively larger topologies. The data augmentation and analysis processes were executed on a single machine equipped with 10 cores, and 16 GB of unified LPDDR5 memory, offering up to 200 GB/s bandwidth.

External Python scripts written in version 3.13.2 were used to generate the augmented datasets and interface with a Neo4j database running version 5.21.0. The database was containerized using Docker version 20.10.16 and orchestrated through Docker Compose version 2.6.0. The Awesome Procedures On Cypher (APOC) plugin version 2025.01.0 and the Graph Data Science (GDS) plugin version 2.13 were enabled to support advanced query execution and graph metric computation. Communication between the scripts and the database was handled using the `neo4j-rust-ext` library version 6.0.2.0.

Each advanced metric was computed ten times for every evaluated configuration of UEs and flows to ensure statistical consistency. In the largest evaluated configuration—corresponding to 65,536 UEs and 1,048,576 flows—the resulting network graph contained 1,736,513 nodes and 2,846,143 edges, as shown in Figure 7.

B. Comparative Evaluation of Advanced Spatial Metrics

This section analyses the computational performance and scalability of the proposed advanced spatial metrics in comparison with the classical betweenness centrality baseline. The computation time of Risk Centrality $RC(v)$ and Betweenness Centrality $BC(v)$ was measured under varying numbers of UEs and network flows, as shown in Figure 8. Across all configurations, RC exhibits higher computation times than BC , primarily due to its multi-dimensional formulation. For smaller network instances, such as 64 UEs and 16,384 flows, RC completes in 0.21 seconds compared to 0.07 seconds for BC . At 65,536 UEs and 1,048,576 flows, RC requires 23.4 seconds while BC completes in 9.56 seconds.

The analysis of Security-Aware Betweenness $SAB(v)$ follows a similar methodology, as shown in Figure 9. SAB consistently requires more processing time than BC across all configurations. In the smallest configuration (64 UEs and 16,384 flows), SAB completes in 0.23 seconds compared to 0.07 seconds for BC . In the largest evaluated network (65,536

Fig. 11. Runtime comparison of Betweenness Centrality $BC(v)$ and Network Service Criticality $NSC(s)$ computations as the system scales with the number of UEs and network flows.

Fig. 12. Runtime comparison of Betweenness Centrality $BC(v)$ and Aggregated Infrastructure Criticality $AIC(s)$ computations as the system scales with the number of UEs and network flows.

metrics simultaneously.

C. Efficiency of CSAP in Retrieving Software Vulnerabilities

Efficient retrieval of software vulnerabilities from large-scale knowledge graphs is essential for maintaining accurate situational awareness in dynamic network environments. A series of experiments were conducted using datasets of increasing size, ranging from 4,096 to 262,144 software versions. The retrieval was tested under three concurrency levels—32, 64, and 128 parallel processes—to examine the impact of parallelism on performance.

The results obtained under 32 concurrent processes (Figure 13) establish the baseline behavior. For small to moderate datasets, execution times remain below one hour, with the minimum observed around 0.28 hours for 4,096 software

versions and a batch size of 32. As the dataset grows to 262,144 software versions, the total retrieval time increases to 18.20 hours. An optimal batch size consistently emerges between 16 and 32, minimizing total runtime.

Fig. 13. Runtime scaling of the vulnerability search workflow with total software versions and batch size per process (up to 32 concurrent processes).

When the number of concurrent processes doubles to 64 (Figure 14), a nearly proportional improvement in performance is observed. For example, retrieving vulnerabilities for 262,144 software versions decreases from 18.20 hours to 9.10 hours—an almost linear speed-up.

Fig. 14. Runtime scaling of the vulnerability search workflow with total software versions and batch size per process (up to 64 concurrent processes).

Further increasing concurrency to 128 processes (Figure 15) approximately halves the total execution times. With this setup, CSAP retrieves vulnerabilities for 262,144 software versions in 4.55 hours. The same performance envelope is maintained: optimal results continue to occur for batch sizes between 16 and 32.

Overall, CSAP's graph-based vulnerability retrieval component exhibits robust parallel scalability and predictable performance. The results confirm that the retrieval architecture is well-suited for real-time or near-real-time operation in large-scale network environments. For most deployment scenarios,

Fig. 15. Runtime scaling of the vulnerability search workflow with total software versions and batch size per process (up to 128 concurrent processes).

configurations using 64 concurrent processes with batch sizes between 16 and 32 provide the most efficient trade-off, delivering fast vulnerability retrieval while maintaining system stability and resource efficiency.

D. Scalability Test of Increasing Number of Flows to Stress CSAP

The scalability evaluation of CSAP’s flow fetch and store operations was initially presented in our prior conference work [6]. The results are reproduced and extended here with updated figures for completeness, as they form an essential baseline for understanding the platform’s operational performance.

To evaluate how well CSAP scales under increasing workloads, a series of tests measured how the fetch time and the store time change as the batch size grows from 1,000 to 10,000 flows.

Figure 16 (left) illustrates how fetch time varies with different batch sizes. The trend shows a roughly linear increase across the entire range: at 10,000 flows the fetch time is approximately 0.5 seconds, growing to around 4.5 seconds at 100,000 flows. Since CSAP retrieves flows in batches of fixed size, this learn growth confirms that retrieval overhead remains predictable and controlled even at larger scales.

Figure 16 (right) shows the time taken to store the retrieved flows in the Neo4j database. Store times also grow linearly, from approximately 1 second at 10,000 flows to around 9 seconds at 100,000 flows. Several outliers were identified in smaller batches due to cold starts of the database; as the database warmed up with subsequent operations, performance stabilized.

These results show that, while storing flows takes longer than fetching them, the overhead is not significant enough to be a performance bottleneck. CSAP’s batch-based fetching strategy ensures smooth operation, and the underlying graph database structure allows for efficient scaling.

E. Latency Introduced for Parsing 6G Traffic

The evaluation of per-byte processing latency for GTP, TCP, and UDP traffic was initially presented in our prior conference work [6]. The results are reproduced here with updated figures for completeness.

This section evaluates the latency introduced by Skydive when analyzing 6G traffic such as GTP, compared to TCP and UDP. Performance was measured by timing the processing of network packets within the `packetToFlow` function. By dividing the total processing time (in microseconds) by the size of the packet (in bytes), *time per byte* in *microseconds per byte* ($\mu\text{s}/\text{byte}$) was calculated.

Figure 17 shows the packet processing *time per byte* for the TCP, UDP, and GTP protocols. TCP has the lowest median processing time and the smallest interquartile range (IQR). UDP has a slightly higher median processing time than TCP, along with a wider IQR. GTP, an encapsulated protocol, has a median and distribution similar to UDP, indicating that the overhead introduced by its decapsulation is not significant. In general, the results suggest that, although encapsulation adds some complexity, its impact on *per-byte* processing time remains comparable to that of non-encapsulated protocols such as UDP.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we addressed the challenge of achieving cyber situational awareness in 6G networks. As part of the 6G-SOC framework, we designed and implemented a topology monitoring system capable of continuously tracking network structure and dynamics. Network traffic was captured and analyzed through the Skydive tool, while the underlying ISIM data model was enhanced to incorporate software vulnerabilities, network flows, and contextual relationships, resulting in the Extended ISIM (EISIM) model. This enriched representation enables CSAP to integrate cyber assets, their fingerprints, and interconnections into a unified, vulnerability-aware network graph.

Through our experiments, we demonstrated that CSAP can efficiently retrieve, store, and correlate network flows and software vulnerabilities, supporting near real-time visibility of security-relevant activity at the granularity of flows and software assets. The system’s performance was evaluated under progressively larger, realistic topologies—derived from a physical test environment and augmented to over 1.7 million nodes and 2.8 million edges—validating its scalability for modern 6G infrastructures.

We further analyzed several advanced spatial metrics, comparing them against traditional betweenness centrality. Results showed that these enhanced metrics provide richer contextual awareness while maintaining acceptable computational overhead, allowing the identification of critical assets not only by structural importance but also by security exposure.

Additionally, our evaluation of the vulnerability retrieval subsystem highlighted the importance of balancing concurrency and batch processing to achieve optimal performance. While configurations with 128 concurrent processes delivered the fastest retrieval times, 32–64 processes offered a more

Fig. 16. Fetch time (left) and store time (right) for batches of Skydive flows of increasing size retrieved from and stored into CSAP. Each data point represents the mean over 10 repetitions; shaded bands indicate ± 1 standard deviation. Both metrics scale linearly up to 100k flows.

Fig. 17. Processing time per byte ($\mu\text{s}/\text{byte}$) for UDP, TCP, and GTP traffic flows captured by the CSAP data collection pipeline. Distributions are estimated over all captured packets; horizontal lines indicate the median. TCP exhibits the lowest and most consistent per-byte processing overhead.

sustainable trade-off between speed and resource utilization, ensuring reliable operation across diverse computational environments.

In addition, we analyzed how the system scales with the number of gNBs and UEs generating traffic, showing that while per-batch fetch and store latencies remain well below workflow intervals, stability ultimately depends on the balance between offered traffic and the scheduled drain rate of the Temporal workflow. Several directions for future work are identified. First, the EISIM graph will serve as the input for a GNN-based anomaly detection layer, enabling automated identification of suspicious patterns in network topology and traffic without requiring labeled attack data. Second, the computed spatial metrics—particularly RC and SAB —will be used to drive cognitive, policy-based response decisions within the 6G-SOC, such as automatically rerouting traffic away from high-risk nodes or triggering mitigation workflows when critical thresholds are exceeded. Third, the current batch-based metric computation will be extended with incremental update algorithms, recomputing only the affected subgraph when topology changes occur, which is expected to reduce computation time significantly for large-scale deployments.

Finally, the integration of CSAP with threat intelligence feeds will be explored to enrich the vulnerability context beyond CVSS scores, incorporating exploitability and active threat data into the risk assessment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been funded by the European Union’s NextGenerationEU, as part of the Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan, supported by Spanish INCIBE (6G-SOC project). This work has been also funded by the RIGOROUS project from the European Union’s Research and Innovation Programme Horizon Europe under grant agreement no. 1011095933. This research has been supported by the Resilmesh project funded by the European Union as part of the Horizon Europe Framework Program (HORIZON), under grant agreement no. 101119681.

REFERENCES

- [1] U. Franke, A. Andreasson, H. Artman, J. Brynielsson, S. Varga, and N. Vilhelm, “Chapter 10 - Cyber situational awareness issues and challenges,” in *Cybersecurity and Cognitive Science*, A. A. Moustafa, Ed. Academic Press, 2022, pp. 235–265.
- [2] H. J. Ofte and S. Katsikas, “Understanding situation awareness in SOCs, a systematic literature review,” *Computers & Security*, vol. 126, p. 103069, 2023.
- [3] S. Noel, E. Harley, K. H. Tam, M. Limiero, and M. Share, “CyGraph: Graph-Based Analytics and Visualization for Cybersecurity,” *Handbook of Statistics*, vol. 35, pp. 117–167, 2016.
- [4] M. Husák, L. Sadlek, S. Špaček, M. Laštovička, M. Javorník, and J. Komárková, “CRUSOE: A toolset for cyber situational awareness and decision support in incident handling,” *Computers & Security*, vol. 115, p. 102609, 2022.
- [5] D. Shahjee and N. Ware, “Integrated network and security operation center: A systematic analysis,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 27 881–27 898, 2022.
- [6] J. A. Pastor, M. Husák, J. B. Bernabe, and A. Skarmeta, “Real-Time Network Cyber Situational Awareness in B5G Networks,” in *2025 IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, 2025, pp. 591–596.
- [7] J. B. Bernabé, B. Lee, M. Husák, L. Sadlek, B. Stojanović, M. Somma, J. Inacio de Oliveira, E. P. Nieto, P. F. Saura, A. Skarmeta, and V. H. La, “The Resilmesh Architecture: Situation Aware Enabled Cyber Resilience for Dispersed, Heterogenous Cyber Systems,” in *2025 IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, 2025, pp. 621–626.
- [8] B. Morin, L. Mé, H. Debar, and M. Ducassé, “M2D2: A formal data model for IDS alert correlation,” in *International Workshop on Recent Advances in Intrusion Detection*. Springer, 2002, pp. 115–137.

- [9] J. Holsopple, S. J. Yang, and B. Argauer, "Virtual terrain: a security-based representation of a computer network," in *Data Mining, Intrusion Detection, Information Assurance, and Data Networks Security*, 2008, p. 69730E.
- [10] J. Komárková, M. Husák, M. Laštovička, and D. Tovarňák, "CRUSOE: Data Model for Cyber Situational Awareness," in *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security*, 2018, pp. 36:1–36:10.
- [11] I. Sanchez-Navarro, J. Bernal Bernabe, J. M. Alcaraz-Calero, and Q. Wang, "Advanced spatial network metrics for cognitive management of 5G networks," *Soft Computing*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 215–232, 2021.
- [12] P. K. Gkonis, N. Nomikos, P. Trakadas, L. Sarakis, G. Xylouris, X. Masip-Bruin, and J. Martrat, "Leveraging network data analytics function and machine learning for data collection, resource optimization, security and privacy in 6G networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 21 320–21 336, 2024.
- [13] L. A. B. Sanguino and R. Uetz, "Software vulnerability analysis using CPE and CVE," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1705.05347, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1705.05347>
- [14] S. H. Houmb, V. N. Franqueira, and E. A. Engum, "Quantifying security risk level from cvss estimates of frequency and impact," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 83, no. 9, pp. 1622–1634, 2010.
- [15] E. Chang, F. Gottwalt, and Y. Zhang, "Cyber Situational Awareness for CPS, 5G and IoT," in *Frontiers in Electronic Technologies*, S. Prabhakaran, N. M. Thalmann, and V. S. Kanchana Bhaaskaran, Eds. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2017, pp. 147–161.
- [16] N. Slamnik-Kriještorac, F. Z. Yousaf, G. M. Yilma, R. Halili, M. Liebisch, and J. M. Marquez-Barja, "Edge-aware cloud-native service for enhancing back situation awareness in 5g-based vehicular systems," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 660–677, 2024.
- [17] D. Grimm, M. Zink, M. Schindewolf, and E. Sax, "Cyber situational awareness in vehicle security operations: Holistic monitoring and a data model," in *2024 20th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, 2024, pp. 1–7.
- [18] Q. Li, H. Tang, Z. Liu, J. Li, X. Xu, and W. Sun, "Optimal resource allocation of 5g machine-type communications for situation awareness in active distribution networks," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 4187–4197, 2022.
- [19] S. Yang, D. Yin, X. Song, X. Dong, G. Manogaran, G. Mastorakis, C. X. Mavromoustakis, and J. M. Batalla, "Security situation assessment for massive MIMO systems for 5G communications," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 98, pp. 25–34, 2019.
- [20] M. Laštovička, M. Husák, P. Velan, T. Jirsík, and P. Čeleda, "Passive operating system fingerprinting revisited: Evaluation and current challenges," *Computer Networks*, vol. 229, p. 109782, 2023.
- [21] M. Laštovička, M. Husák, and L. Sadlek, "Network monitoring and enumerating vulnerabilities in large heterogeneous networks," in *NOMS 2020 - 2020 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [22] B. A. Cheikes, D. Waltermire, and K. Scarfone, "Common platform enumeration: Naming specification version 2.3," *NIST Interagency Report*, vol. 7695, no. 8, 2011.
- [23] J. Collins, *GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP)*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2019, pp. 1–3.
- [24] T. Li, D. Farinacci, S. P. Hanks, D. Meyer, and P. S. Traina, "Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE)," RFC 2784, Mar. 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc2784>
- [25] M. Mahalingam, D. Dutt, K. Duda, P. Agarwal, L. Kreeger, T. Sridhar, M. Bursell, and C. Wright, "Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network (VXLAN): A Framework for Overlaying Virtualized Layer 2 Networks over Layer 3 Networks," RFC 7348, Aug. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc7348>
- [26] J. Gross, I. Ganga, and T. Sridhar, "Geneve: Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation," RFC 8926, Nov. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc8926>
- [27] A. Viswanathan, E. C. Rosen, and R. Callon, "Multiprotocol Label Switching Architecture," RFC 3031, Jan. 2001. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc3031>

José Antonio Pastor Valera received the B.S. degree in Computer Science from the University of Murcia, Spain. He is currently a Researcher and Software Engineer with the Department of Information and Communications Engineering, University of Murcia, where he contributes to the development of a cyber situational awareness platform. His research interests include cyber situational awareness, cognitive and adaptive security, real-time threat detection, and the modeling and analysis of complex infrastructures in next-generation (6G) network environments.

Martin Husák is a researcher at the Institute of Computer Science at Masaryk University, Czech Republic, and a member of the university's security team (CSIRT-MU). He was also a visiting researcher at The University of Texas at San Antonio, USA and Florida Atlantic University, USA. His research interests are related to cyber situational awareness and incident response with a special focus on incident triage and application of graph-based data analytics and recommender systems. He was leading the development of the CRUSOE toolset that aims at supporting cyber situational awareness in computer networks by collecting and aggregating data on the hosts and using them for decision support in incident handling.

Jesús García Rodríguez received the B.S. degree in Mathematics and the B.S., M.Sc., and Ph.D. degrees in Computer Science from the University of Murcia. He is a Postdoctoral Researcher at the Department of Information and Communications Engineering, where he has participated in several EU projects like OLYMPUS, ERATOSTHENES, ENTRUST, and LICORICE. His research interests involve privacy-enhancing and security technologies, including cryptographic developments and their application to the Internet of Things. Currently, he is continuing his research on secure and privacy-preserving identity and trust management in areas such as post-quantum cryptography, IoT and 5G+ technologies.

Jorge Bernal Bernabé received the MSc, Master, and Ph.D. in Computer Science as well as an MBA from the University of Murcia (Spain). He was granted the "Best PhD Thesis Award" from the University of Murcia, a postdoctoral research grant funded by INCIBE (Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute) and an AXA Postdoctoral Scholarship awarded by the AXA Research Fund. Since February 2023 he has been an Associate Professor at the University of Murcia. Author of more than 45 papers published in JCR-indexed impact journals. His scientific activity is mainly devoted to security, trust, and privacy management in distributed systems and networks.

Antonio Skarmeta received the B.S. degree (Hons.) and the M.S. degree in computer science from the University of Granada, Spain, and the Ph.D. degree in computer science from the University of Murcia, Spain. He has been the Head of the Research Group ANTS since its creation in 1995. Since 2009, he has been a Professor at the University of Murcia. His research interests include integration of security services, identity, the IoT, and smart cities. He has also participated in standardization for IETF, ISO, and ETSI, and has worked on different national and international research projects in the networking, security, and IoT areas.